

Development of Monitoring and Analysis Tools for the Huawei Cloud Storage

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Abstract

CERN is the largest research centre for particle physics research in the world. Experiments generate large amounts of data which must be stored, processed and analysed. The storage solutions should provide large data capacity, scalability and reliability.

The Openlab CERN-Huawei partnership aims at testing and evaluating the performance of the Huawei Universal Distributed Storage system. Benchmarking and monitoring tools are developed to investigate the storage system behaviour.

This report describes the upgrades done for the monitoring and analysis tools used by the Huawei cloud storage system at CERN. The first part of the report describes the additions done to the monitoring system of the cloud storage. The rest of the report describes the improvements done for scripts for listing files on the storage and monitoring their size.

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1 Introduction

The Huawei Storage system, placed at CERN's computing centre, consists of two UDS (Universal Distributed Storage) systems [1]. The first UDS (Figure 1) has 768 TB of storage space divided over 384 storage nodes and controlled by seven controller nodes. The second UDS (Figure 2) is a newer generation with newer software. It has 1200 TB of storage space divided over 300 storage nodes and controlled by four controller nodes. Both systems make use of the S3 (Simple Storage Service) protocol. S3 provides an API for making requests to the system by using HTTP methods such as GET, PUT or LIST. The log analysis and monitoring is carried out for both systems. Log files are continuously generated by the storage systems in order to understand the system behaviour.

Figure 1. First Huawei UDS

Figure 2. Second Huawei UDS

2 General Monitoring System for the Huawei Cloud Storage

The aim of the monitoring system is to understand the behaviour of the storage systems and to identify events, such as file operations and error messages generated by the storage software, and when they happen. This is done by retrieving log files from the storage then parsing and analysing them. Figure 3 shows the steps followed in the monitoring process and the programming language used in each step.

Figure 3. Monitoring process steps

The storage monitoring that previously existed enabled log files downloading and parsing for the first Huawei UDS. The new feature that was added was making the monitoring system a general one for both Huawei storages. Parameters that are specific for each UDS, such as IP addresses of front-end nodes, available file operations, etc., are read from configuration files created per UDS. Thus, the monitoring system can be used for both storages.

2.1 Log files retrieval

Log files contain entries of events, such as file operations, errors or status messages, which the storage software has produced together with their timestamps. Two types of log files are retrieved from the storage system; access logs and java logs. Access logs contain information about file operations that have been performed inside the storage system, such as GET or DELETE a file. Figure 4 shows an example of an access log entry. Java logs contain entries from the storage system software. Any kind of error or event that is logged can be found in these files.

```

obs-osc r [08/Aug/2014 03:33:54.821 +0000] 10.40.129.2:5080
128.142.33.221:54462 - 4846FB92907000000145AD72643F0070
4846FB92907000000147B3AE0FFD7380 REST.GET.OBJECT 4k-291 /ssheikki-
downloadtest/4k-291 200 - 8 8 - - - 176 0 4000 text/plain
"31c1164bf090974524f6c689acce48d6" 4415 4000 - Fri, 08 Aug 2014 03:33:54 GMT
- - - - - 5 1 0 0 0 null null null null - - null null null 0
  
```

Figure 4. An example of an access log entry for second Huawei UDS

There are two options for retrieving logs from the storage: either get the most recent logs only or get historic logs too. Retrieval is done using secure copy from the remote host to the local host while preserving all original file attributes, such as time it was modified and accessed.

The existing script enabled retrieving log files from the first UDS. The script now is general and enables retrieving logs from either storage system.

2.2 Log files analysis

Analysing logs is an important part of understanding the behaviour of the storage system. Log files are parsed to display a readable summary of the events occurring in a given interval of time. This is done for both types of log files.

Events are extracted from the log files, together with the number of times each event occurred. If the requested range to be analysed is longer than the contents of the most recent log file, older log files are appended as needed. An example of the summary resulting from parsing access logs of the first UDS is shown in Figure 5. The summary shows the number of times every event occurred for every front-end node.

```
$ python analyse_logs.py old 90*60 "28/Aug/2014 20:30:00"
Summary of 10.40.65.3*.obs.access.log files.
All range: '11/Feb/2014 22:19:24' and '29/Aug/2014 08:04:07' (17138683 seconds).
Req range: '28/Aug/2014 19:00:00' and '28/Aug/2014 20:30:00' (5400 seconds).

Number of...          Front end node...
                        #1      #2      #3      #4      #5      #6      #7      =SUM
Total in range:        168995  153788  160811  176757  177543  163799  170482  =1172175
403 -                  29      23      36      43      40      35      36      =242
OSC V100R001C00       7        7        7        8        8        7        7        =51
REST.GET.OBJECT        0        20       0        0        0        0        12       =32
REST.HEAD.OBJECT      147524  131894  139979  154691  153665  141664  148802  =1018219
REST.PUT.OBJECT        21435   21844   20789   22015   23830   22093   21625   =153631
Unclassified:         0        0        0        0        0        0        0        =0
Old entries:          90944   64742   147605  358773  65280   45855   118322  =118322

Summary of 10.40.65.3*.obs.log files.
All range: '27/Aug/2014 19:44:27' and '29/Aug/2014 08:04:07' (130780 seconds).
Req range: '28/Aug/2014 19:00:00' and '28/Aug/2014 20:30:00' (5400 seconds).
```

Figure 5. First UDS analyzing access logs summary

2.3 Plotting events

Data from log files can be visualized by a previously developed plotting tool [2]. A graph showing the distribution of a chosen file operation during the given interval based on log file entries can be drawn. The graph can be plotted separately for each frontend node or as a sum of all nodes. Figure 6 shows the plot of the same data that was analysed in Figure 5.

Figure 6. Plotting a REST.HEAD.OBJECT event for the first UDS

3 Parallelization of File-listing Script

The file-listing script is used to list files per user account stored on the Huawei systems. The existing script was slow as it used one thread. The improvement made was to increase the speed by using several threads. Two different implementations were tried to get the best speedup.

3.1 Parallelization using one thread per user account

The first approach to the parallelization of the file-listing script is to use one thread per user account so that all accounts are analysed in parallel. Each thread writes its account data in a file. When all threads are done, all files are concatenated to one file as shown in Figure 7.

3.2 Parallelization using pool of processes

The second approach to parallelization and speed improvement is to define a pool of worker processes to list files per bucket. Each thread writes its bucket data in a file. There are usually many more buckets than processes. As soon as a process completes its listing for a bucket, it is assigned another one until all buckets have been completed. The processes then terminate and all files are concatenated as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Parallelization first approach

Figure 8. Parallelization second approach

The number of worker processes can be controlled in order to get the highest speedup. Figure 9 shows the execution times corresponding to different pool sizes. The script was tested for 21 user accounts with a hundred buckets each. The total number of files was 3757369 files. The tests were run on a server equipped with 48GB of RAM memory and 24 Intel Xeon 2.27 GHz cores.

Figure 9. Execution time vs. number of processes

Figure 10 shows a comparison for the execution times of the original script and the two parallelization approaches. In the second approach the thread pool was created with 21 processes. The same previous accounts were used for testing. The second parallelization approach gives the highest speedup; the average speedup is 6.5 for 21 processes.

Figure10. Execution times for original file-listing and the two parallelization approaches

4 Size Monitoring

It is sometime necessary not only to list the files and their number but also to calculate the total size of the files stored in the cloud storage.

Given the high speedup of the parallelised file-listing script, calculation of size of files is added to the parallel script as a new feature. The existing code for calculating size also used one thread.

Figure 11 shows a comparison for the execution times of the original script for size calculation and the parallelised file-listing script with the added size calculation. The size calculation was added to the second parallelization approach (section 3.2). The same accounts used in the previous chapter were also used for testing.

Figure 11. Execution times for original size calculation script and the parallelized script

5 Conclusions

The analysis and monitoring system of CERN Openlab Huawei cloud storage has been improved to provide a general monitoring system, which allows log file analysis and event visualization for both CERN Openlab Huawei cloud storage generations. Moreover, a parallelisation technique has been applied to the file-listing script in order to speed it up, by achieving a 6.5 factor of improvement. A new feature has been included to retrieve the total size of the files already stored in both cloud storages. In the future, a storage node analysis for collecting CPU and disk metrics would be interesting to complete the current analysis system.

6 References

- [1] Zotes Resines M., Heikkilä S.S., Duellmann D., Adde G., Toebbicke R., Hughes J. & Wang L. "Evaluation of the Huawei UDS cloud storage system for CERN specific data", Journal of Physics: Conference Series Vol. 513(4), 2014
- [2] Lindqvist C., "Improved Metrics Collection and Correlation for the CERN Cloud Storage Test Framework", CERN Openlab summer student report, 2013.